

THERMALLY CONDUCTIVE NETWORKS IN POLYMERS FOR COMPOSITE MISSILE APPLICATIONS

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SUMMARY

Higher thermal conductivity is necessary to provide composite missile structure designers the capability to move heat from electronics. The Aviation and Missile Research Development and Engineering Center is researching techniques to improve the through thickness thermal conductivity of carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites without sacrificing their inherent specific strength.

Keywords: thermal management, fiber, composites, conductivity, nanocomposites

INTRODUCTION

Thermal management requirements continue to challenge composite missile structure designers. Heat generated by sensor and guidance electronics must be removed to prevent overheating and malfunction. This can be accomplished more readily in metal structures but fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites require the incorporation of heat sink materials which add weight and bulk to the system. Traditional aluminum missile structures have a thermal conductivity on the order of 180 W/mK. This level of conductivity provides an excellent heat sink for on-board electronics. Carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites have a thermal conductivity of less than 1 W/mK in the cross-ply direction. Research is continuing at the Aviation and Missile Research Development and Engineering Center (AMRDEC) to improve this through-thickness thermal conductivity.

MATERIAL

This research explores some of the techniques and materials with potential to improve the through-thickness thermal conductivity of fiber reinforced polymers. Continuous carbon fiber (PAN-based) reinforced polymer composites have thermal conductivities on the order of 10 W/m-K in the plane of the carbon fibers. Through-thickness thermal conductivity of these composites are dependent on the polymer matrix and therefore exhibit conductivities on the order of .3 W/m-K.

Experience from previous research involved with dispersion of particles has shown only moderate improvements in thermal conductivity through polymers and fiber reinforced polymers [1-3]. Typical silver and copper filled epoxies have a thermal conductivity of up to 4 W/m-K. To achieve a through thickness thermal conductivity of 20 W/m-K or greater, a continuous phase of material must be inserted or generated that spans the thickness of the composite. To achieve this goal, the following techniques were chosen: Z-pinning, integration of patterned carbon nanotube arrays, and 3D braiding of pitch based fibers.

Z-Pinning

High thermal conductivity materials were selected for use as through-thickness pins that would be integrated into the filament winding process. This process has become known as Z-pinning [4] which involves the insertion of pins through the entire thickness of a composite laminate. Figure 1 is a graphic representation of a composite laminate test coupon with z-pins in place. Filament winding is a common process used for fabrication of continuous fiber reinforced composites, especially cylinders. It is used in the fabrication of rocket motor cases and missile airframes. This process is well described elsewhere. [5]

Figure 1: Model of Z-pinning thermal conductivity test specimen

Table 1 shows the materials selected for evaluation as pins through the composite laminate. Metals would not be practical in a real world environment because of thermal expansion mismatch and corrosion but copper was evaluated as a benchmark.

Pin Material	K (W/mK)	ρ (lb/in3)
Cu cold drawn	385	0.324
K13D2U Mitsubishi	800	0.057
K13C2U Mitsubishi	620	0.057
K63A12 Mitsubishi	220	0.057
YS95A-60S	600	0.057
YS90A-60S	500	0.057
CN90-60S	500	0.057
CN80-A2S	320	0.057
Annealed pyrolytic graphite k1	800	0.079
Annealed pyrolytic graphite k2	1100	0.079
Annealed pyrolytic graphite k3	1500	0.079

Table 1. Z-pinning materials for through thickness thermal conductivity in composites

Pitch based fibers from Nippon Graphite Fiber Corporation and Mitsubishi Chemical were selected. U.S. based suppliers discontinued the production of pitch based fibers. Annealed pyrolytic graphite was also chosen as a pin material. Several different levels of annealing for the pyrolytic graphite were chosen and evaluated for ease of processing. Higher levels of annealing reduce the structural integrity of the pins.

Figure 2: Z-pinning effect on thermal conductivity in composites using rule of mixtures

Patterned Aligned Nanotube Arrays

Carbon nanotubes have shown thermal conductivities from 3000 to 6000 W/m-K [6,7]. If this extraordinary conductivity could be integrated into the composite laminate, a through-thickness conductivity solution could be realized. Initial trials attempting to apply the arrays into inter-laminar regions of filament-wound composites have resulted in limited success.

Harnessing the thermal conductivity of carbon nanotubes on the macro scale has not been accomplished to date. For laminated composites, dispersing the nanotubes in resin systems results in too many interfaces to accommodate phonon transfer. Aligned nanotube arrays in the interlaminar regions shows promise, but interfaces are also too prevalent. Current work underway at AMRDEC will pursue patterned aligned nanotube arrays in the form of a “bed of pins.” The pins will be designed to penetrate through several layers of carbon fibers to provide a pathway for heat transfer.

Figure 3: Patterned aligned multi-wall nanotube array (courtesy Prof. Mauricio Terrones, Nestor Perea-Lopez, Ana Laura ELIAS, Advanced Materials Dept. IPICYT)

One of the many obstacles that will need to be overcome for the use of aligned nanotube arrays as “pins” is the nanotube density. Currently, the best nanotube density is approximately 10 percent. If the nanotube has a thermal conductivity of 6000 W/m-K, then the pin conductivity will be 600 W/m-K as a best case. This can be achieved with other forms of carbon so the trade off of cost and ease of processing must be explored.

PROCESSING

Filament Winding

Filament Winding is the composite fabrication technique most conducive to cylindrical structures like rocket motor cases and missile airframes. One of the challenges associated with this effort will be to integrate the high conductivity materials into the composite processing techniques. Some of the important considerations of composites processing will be detailed here.

The biggest challenge of integrating the high thermal conductivity materials into the composite materials will be minimizing damage to the composite laminate and the conductive materials. Filament winding relies on fiber tension for composite layer compaction. As the fiber tow is wound around a cylindrical mandrel, compaction of the layers is a function of fiber tension and mandrel radius. See figure 4.

Figure 4: Compaction pressure vs. mandrel diameter for filament winding process

For this effort, the high conductivity pins will be incorporated into the composite laminate during the filament winding process. A specially designed aluminum mandrel has been fabricated that will allow a section of foam to be used to hold the pins in place during winding. The tension in the carbon fiber tows and the resulting compaction pressure will require pins with enough structural integrity to survive processing.

The carbon fiber tows will “wind” over the high conductivity pins which will be inserted into the foam in appropriate patterns and densities. See Figure 5. This arrangement will provide the best opportunity for the carbon fiber tows to lay down under tension and allow the pins to protrude through the laminate. The pins will be 1 inch long with 0.8 inches of the length embedded in the foam to provide stability and support of the pins. This approach is expected to provide the best opportunity to maximize pin density and minimize fiber and pin damage.

Figure 5: Arrangement of pins for filament winding based on a 20° wind angle with 400 W/m-K pins for a laminate conductivity of 20 W/m-K

Patterned aligned nanotube arrays will be processed much like the z pins. The arrays are not expected to survive the rigors of the filament winding process. To improve the rigidity and toughness of the arrays, infiltration with polymers will be explored. The optimum set-up would be for the nanotube arrays to be infiltrated with polymer and taken to gel point. The goal would be to have a pin that consisted of nanotubes and a polymer that would flow during the cure of the composite laminate.

CONCLUSION

Carbon fiber polymer composites have acceptable thermal conductivity along the length of the fiber, but the inter-laminar matrix resin and lower thermal conductivity across the width of the carbon fiber lead to poor overall cross-ply or through-thickness conductivity. This effort evaluates several technologies with the potential to dramatically improve the through-thickness conductivity of fiber reinforced polymer composites.

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References

1. J. Hone, M.C.Llaguno, M.J. Biercuk, A.T. Johnson, B. Batlogg, Z. Benes, and J.E. Fisher, "Thermal properties of carbon nanotubes and nanotube-based materials," *Appl. Phys. A. Mater. Sci. Process.*, vol. 74, pp.339-343, 2002.
2. M.J. Biercuk, M.C. Llaguno, M. Radsavljevic, J.K. Hun, A.T. Johnson, and J.E. Fischer, "Carbon nanotube composites for thermal management," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 80, no. 2, pp. 2767-2769, 2002.
3. E.T. Thostenson, Z. Ren, and T.W. Chou, "Advances in the science and technology," *Composite Sci. Technology*, vol. 61, pp. 1899-1912, 2001.
4. C.A. Steeves, N.A. Fleck, "In-plane properties of composite laminates with through-thickness pin reinforcement," *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, vol. 43, pp.3197-3212, 2006.
5. Peters, Humphrey, Foral, *Filament Winding Composite Structure Fabrication*, 6th Edition, Society for the Advancement of Material and Process Engineering, 1991.
6. E.S. Choi, J.S. Brooks, D.L. Eaton, M.S. Aal-Haik, M.Y. Hussaini, H. Garmestani, D. Li, and K. Dahmen, "Enhancement of thermal and electrical properties of carbon nanotube polymer composites by magnetic field processing," *Journal of Appl. Physics*, vol. 94, no. 9, pp.6034-6039, 2003.
7. S. Berber, Y.K. Kwon, and D.Tomanek, "Unusually high thermal conductivity of carbon nanotubes," *Phys. Rev. Letters*, vol. 84, no. 20, pp. 4613-4616, 2000.